

The De-Central Bank in Decentralized Finance: A Case Study of MakerDAO

Online Appendix

1. Structure of the interviews

Opening

- Welcoming the interviewee, thanking for their time and participation.
- Introducing ourselves.
- Presenting the structure of the interview: Informed consent disclaimer. History and expertise, presenting the artifact, questioning the artifact, closing the interview.

Informed Consent

- Interview will be recorded for future reference – Start the recording, ask again (on tape).
- Results and quotes will be published anonymously, mentioning expertise (DeFi & monetary)

Work History and Expertise

- Give the interviewee the opportunity to introduce themselves.
- Biographic data: Name, Position/Years of experience, expertise (DAOs vs monetary theory)
- Evaluation of the interviewee's expertise at the intersection of monetary theory, DeFi/DAOs

Presenting the Artifact

- Introducing the MakerDAO ecosystem (Dai stable coin, MKR governance, collateralization)
- Introducing the Bretton Woods system, the 'gold coin metaphor for bitcoin', the gold bullion standard, and the gold exchange standard, we are in free floating exchange rate

Questioning the Artifact

- Covering first thoughts that come to mind
- Evaluating whether the comparison holds
 - Does the table hold? Are we the only ones?
 - Is it complete? What should be added?
 - Questioning in which areas the comparison might fail
- Questioning to which extent these problems might be salvageable
- Covering final words that come to mind and future steps

Closing the Interview

- Are there any things the interviewee wants to add?
- Thank the interviewee for their participation – stop the recording
- Close the interview

2. Interviewees

#	Background	Field	Relevant Experience
1	Distributed Ledger Technologies & Decentralized Finance	Research	3 years
2	Distributed Ledger Technologies & Decentralized Finance	Industry	2 years
3	Distributed Ledger Technologies	Industry	2 years
4	Economics	Research	3 years
5	Economics	Research	6 years
6	Economics	Industry	4 years

3. Central Insights

The central improvements of our initial overview of the MakerDAO ecosystem, and our comparison of the different monetary regimes with MakerDAO were as follows:

Overview of the MakerDAO ecosystem

- Structure of the different operative actors (adoption, governance, and decentralization)
- Simplification of the overall overview
- Inclusion of benevolent regulators
- Relevance of competitors (stakeholders in alternative decentralized finance applications)
- The implications of open innovation on MakerDAO and vice versa

Comparison of monetary regimes

- Separation of primary and secondary actors
- The interdependency of value and governance (Improved governance creates higher value and higher value necessitates better governance.
- Stabilization: Collateralization rates and stabilization fees as an individual risk preference
- Relevance of NFTs in the pricing of assets and multi-collaterals
- The governance and financial implications of an environment with acquirable cote shares